

PACIFICUS

A Literary Magazine (Print & e-Publication)

Volume I, Issue II | A Quarterly Publication

ISSN (Online): 3082-4079 | ISSN (Print): 3082-4060

Publisher: Binas Publishing

Email: binasbookers2013@gmail.com

JACKIELOU V. PANTALEON

Teacher I
Mamis Elementary School
jackielou.pantaleon@deped.gov.ph

SHEILA MAE C. SEMACON

Teacher I
Cauwayanan Elementary School
semaconshielamaecastillo@gmail.com

MONICA L. MONTALBAN

Teacher I
Bebiano Alba Elementary School
monica.montalban@deped.gov.ph

CRISTY V. PLAZA

Teacher I
Labisma National High School
cristy.plaza@deped.gov.ph

CARL JOSEPH D. MONTERO

monterocarljoaeph78@gmail.com

JOAN T. DE GUZMAN

Teacher I
Tagasaka National High School
joan.deguzman001@deped.gov.ph

DR RIO S. CONSIGNA-ADORABLE

Dean, College of Teacher Education
Andres Soriano Colleges of Bislig
rioconsign82@gmail.com

“INTEGRATING TECHNOLOGY IN CURRICULUM DESIGN: A FRAMEWORK FOR 21ST CENTURY LEARNING”

Integrating technology in curriculum design this 21st century is quite challenging because of the following reasons that the end users such as the teachers and the students should have the necessary access of the program and its application with internet connectivity; considering it needs trainings to teachers that entails big budget, and how the project should be sustained, monitored and evaluated.

Designing a curriculum which is technology- based could be something to explore since curriculum is dynamic. What could be applicable today could not be the same ten years from now. This means that the curriculum is designed in such a way that it is maybe applicable in the long run. Designing a curriculum requires huge budget from the government resources, and in order to avoid wastage of government money, the curriculum designers must have a thorough study from the previous curriculum and how does this curriculum would affect as to its content, structure, objective and its implementation on the present curriculum being designed which is technology- based.

It needs then, an expert in curriculum designing and at the same time expert in the programming technology that suits the need and trend of the 21st century learners. Law makers should set aside personal interest over public interest, because what is at stake, is the future of the next generation, and it is how a curriculum design affects the learner's achievement and what could possibly influence and describe of what type of generation a nation could have for the next decade. The type of political leaders that what we have in our country today could be somewhat impacted from the curriculum design 20 years ago.

The importance of integrating technology in curriculum design describes what type of learners do we have nowadays which are too personal, managed multiple responsibilities, digitally expert, and who are fast learner in terms of comprehension of application and operating the technology. In other words, it's part of their culture, thus, this makes the learners easier to learn and comfortable to adapt innovation and approaches of some learning tools being introduced in integrating technology in the curriculum design. Teachers can easily adapt integrating curriculum design because teachers by nature are creative, aside from being diligent, hardworking and the most highly dedicated public employee in the public sector.

Using technology in curriculum design, this 21st century develops student critical, problem solving and cooperative skills and preparing the learners to supply the world market for employment. When a curriculum is developed using integrating technology and this technology is design learners to analyze, interpret which are more engaging, thus, the ability of the learners to think and solve problems are developed and improved, and in the process, as these learners integrate in the mainstream of the society, the chain of poverty is broken down. One become employee or a worker of any sector and as a partner or national building that in the broadest sense, it contributes the national economy of the country.

Therefore, integrating technology in the curriculum design this 21st century must be a priority of the Department of Education. The agency has a big role on training and development, curriculum alignment, monitoring and digital enhancement skill of teachers. Relevant learning experience for students in the 21st characterized experience as personal, genuine, significant content, relatable and entertaining topics and also give feedback and materials which the learner can give reactions and at must learner are enjoying and therefore teachers could have been the best practice for technology integration.

There could have numerous frameworks based on research on integrating technology in curriculum design this 21st century in teaching academic subjects describe as knowledge and skills and preparing the learners to be more competent I order to achieve full and balance life. Education is the foundation of life. It plays a vital role to sustain the growth and development of a country, so that world leaders sit down in an international discussion on how to improve its educational system based on framework of curriculum.

The integration of technology as an approach and methodology in curriculum design where the content, process, practices are embedded on the curriculum across all programs and subjects. Infusion approach complements the idea of designing a coherent curriculum for teaching with technology, rather than technology practices being separate from the curriculum, technology practices become part of the content, process and situated practices of teacher educators and candidates across the program. Whatever is the frame work, it still requires in dept research, collaboration from stakeholders, both public and private organization with consultation from various partners including teachers and the learners.

Research on the advent of the Fourth Industrial Revolution shows how technology integration plays a pivotal role in the development of 21st century skills and competences across all subjects and program. It presents pedagogical innovation so that the learners can adjust and sustain to the digital period. World Sustainable

Development goals as the basis of the framework in curriculum design so that humanity and society can survive.

Hence, the pedagogical gap also be addressed such as lack of teacher training, poor curriculum design, limited assessment and evaluation; social and policy gap such as digital barrier socio-cultural and linguistic factor even and inclusivity including limited research, government policy support and funding, thus these gaps requires a collaborative approach that involves, educators, policy makers, stakeholders to ensure that technology integration is effective, efficient, based on social justice, sustainable and align to world sustainable development goal.

In a nutshell, integrating technology in the curriculum design is essential for preparing students for the digital world, when done effectively, technology integration can improve learning experience and increase student academic achievement. However, it requires a meticulous planning, teacher- training and regular evaluation to ensure that the technology is understood that is consistent to curriculum objectives and must see to it that the curriculum design is fair, comprehensive and easy to use for the teachers and the learners this 21st century.